

Impact of 2D/3D Landscape Pattern on Urban Ecological Environment Quality: Explainable Machine Learning Methods

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Summary

It is increasingly important to consider ecological environmental quality (EEQ) in urban design. However, urban expansion is increasingly vertical as well as horizontal. This paper proposes a new set of 2D/3D landscape morphology indicators and a new model for quantifying urban EEQ and applies these within a novel machine learning framework. The preliminary results show that: (1) there is a correlation between landscape morphology indicators and EEQ; (2) the proposed new model has improved accuracy and robustness; (3) a threshold for the landscape morphology indicators can be identified; (4) there are seasonal and scale effects. The above findings may help optimize urban spatial structure, and improve the EEQ in urban areas.

KEYWORDS: explainable machine learning; 2D/3D landscape morphology; Ecological Environmental Quality (EEQ); WB-RSEI model

1. Introduction

As urbanization continues to increase the form of urbanisation and expansion changes from horizontal to vertical expansion due to land pressures. Analysis of city two-dimensional form cannot explain relationships between urban spatial pattern and different Ecological Environment Quality (EEQ) (Qian et al., 2005). Understanding the impact of urban three-dimensional form on EEQ is crucial. Developments in remote sensing and LiDAR technologies provide detailed 3D urban structure data (Yu et al., 2020), building and vegetation height data, which can be used to characterize 3D urban morphology at high resolution, and provide support for analysis of urban 3D morphology on EEQ (Lu et al., 2021).

Urban EEQ directly affects the health and quality of life of residents. Quantitative models are necessary for monitoring urban EEQ levels and preventing ecological risks (Xu et al., 2024). The most widely used EEQ assessment model is the Remote Sensing Ecological Index (RSEI), which is difficult to apply to cities with a large proportion of water bodies (water rich cities) due to its inability to invert the EEQ of water bodies (Ding et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2024). We need an evaluation model suitable for water rich cities.

This study's main innovations include: (1) The use of three-dimensional landscape pattern indicators to capture the impact of three-dimensional urban morphology on EEQ; (2) An EEQ evaluation model applicable to water-rich areas is developed: WB-RSEI; (3) An interpretable machine learning model to analyze the relationship between EEQ and various urban morphology measures. These reveal the impact of landscape morphology indicators on EEQ at multiple scales. These findings may help select the most reasonable landscape indicators for application in urban planning to improve EEQ.

2. Study Methods

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This study used the GEE platform to try to optimize EEQ evaluation model. After obtaining the data, the Interpretable Machine Learning Model was used to analyze the regression between 2D/3D landscape morphological indicators and EEQ at different scales, and the SHAP method was combined to explain the influence and key threshold of each morphological indicator. The specific research framework is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Framework of the research

2.1 Modeling of a new model for ecological environment quality assessment

The most commonly used EEQ evaluation model is RSEI (Xu et al., 2013). This model has the defect of being unable to effectively invert the ecological quality of water areas. This research adds the kernel normalized difference vegetation index (kNDVI) with high vegetation sensitivity and the water abundance index (SPWI) representing the water ecological status to RSEI. It uses the information entropy weighting method to develop a new WB-RSEI model that can better invert the ecological quality of water bodies and densely vegetated areas. The model included the parameters listed in Table 1:

Table 1. Index Calculation List of WB-RSEI

Index	Method of Calculation	Description
kNDVI	$kNDVI = \tanh\left(\left(\frac{Nir - Red}{2\sigma}\right)^2\right)$ $\sigma = 0.5(Nir + Red)$	Kernel Normalized Difference Vegetation Index(kNDVI) based on Hyperbolic Tangent Function operation.(Wang et al., 2024)
WET	$WET = 0.1511Blue + 0.1972Green + 0.3283Red + 0.3407Nir - 0.7117Swir1 - 0.4559Swir2$	Calculation of WET based on tasseled cap transformation algorithm.(Feng et al., 2022)

NDBSI	$NDBSI = \frac{(SI + IBI)}{2}$ $SI = \left[\frac{(Swir1 + Red) - (Blue + Nir)}{(Swir1 + Red) + (Blue + Nir)} \right]$ $IBI = \left\{ \left(\frac{2Swir1}{Swir1 + Nir} \right) - \left[\left(\frac{Nir}{Nir + Red} \right) + \left(\frac{Green}{Green + Swir1} \right) \right] \right\}$ $IBI = \left\{ \left(\frac{2Swir1}{Swir1 + Nir} \right) + \left[\left(\frac{Nir}{Nir + Red} \right) + \left(\frac{Green}{Green + Swir1} \right) \right] \right\}$	NDBSI dryness index combining IBI building index and SI soil index.(Xu et al., 2013)
SPWI	$SPWI = \frac{Nir - Swir2 + Blue}{Nir + Swir2 + Blue}$	Construction of surface potential water abundance index based on water content difference characteristics between Blue Band, Nir Band , and Swir2 Band(Zhou et al., 2023)
LST	$LST = \frac{T}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{\lambda T}{1.438 * 10^{-2}} \right) \ln \varepsilon \right]} - 273.15$	T is the sensor's thermal value, λ means the center wavelength of the thermal infrared band; and ε is the surface emissivity (Ma et al., 2024).
entropy weighting method	$p_{ij} = \frac{Y_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_{ij}}$ $A_j = -\ln(n)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n p_{ij} \ln p_{ij}$ $W_i = \frac{1 - A_i}{k - \sum A_i} (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k)$	pij refers to the proportion of the i-th pixel in the j-th indicator, Yij is the reflectivity of the pixel value i in the j-th indicator, Aj refers to the information entropy value of the corresponding indicator factor, and Wi refers to the final weight of the corresponding indicator factor.(Zhou et al., 2023)

2.2 Selection and Calculation of Landscape Morphology indicators

According to the references and 11 indicators were selected to quantify aspects of ecological quality over 2D and 3D related to landscape fragmentation, landscape complexity, landscape connectivity, and landscape three-dimensionality. See Table 2 for details.

Table 2. Factor Calculation List of Landscape Morphology Pattern

Type	Metrics	Description
	EDI	$EDI = \frac{2\pi rL}{\pi r^2}$ L is the sum of the patch edge lengths, r is the radius of the patch
	SHDI	$SHDI = -\sum P_i \times \ln P_i$ Pi refers to the area proportion of the ith type of plaque
	CONTAG	$CONTAG = \left\{ 1 + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^m \left[(P_i) \left(\frac{g_{jk}}{\sum_{k=1}^m g_{ik}} \right) \right]}{2 \ln(m)} \right\} \times 100$ Pi is the area proportion of the ith patch; gjk is the number of surrounding plates; m is the total number of patches.
2D	COHESION	$COHESION = \left[1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m P_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^m P_{ij} \sqrt{a_{ij}}} \right] \div \left[1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{A}} \right]$ Pi is the proportion of the i-th type of patch; aij is the patch area; A is the total area; m is the total number of patches
	IJI	The higher the IJI value, the better the mixing degree of various plaques. It was calculated using Fragstats 4.2.
	MPS	lower MPS value, greater the plaque change.
	LPI	$LPI = \frac{a_{max}}{A} \times 100$ amax refers to the area of the largest plate, A is the total area

3D	FCH	Obtained using high-precision vegetation canopy height statistics
	VH_mean	

2.3 Interpretable Machine Learning Regression Analysis Method

The XGBoost model was chosen because it has significant advantages in handling nonlinear relationships in data and interaction effects between variables, avoiding overfitting, feature importance analysis, automatic handling of missing values, and flexible parameter adjustment options (Yu et al., 2020). SHAP is a method for interpreting machine learning models. The SHAP value will show a certain trend as the indicator characteristics change, which can be used to explain the influence of the indicator (Sun and Chen, 2017). This study used the XGBoost model to fit the nonlinear fitting relationship between 2D/3D morphological indicators and EEQ.

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! (|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} \left[\int_{S \cup \{i\}} (x_{S \cup \{i\}}) \int_S S(x_S) \right] \quad (1)$$

ϕ_i is the SHAP value of feature i ; F is the set of all features; $f_{S \cup \{i\}}$ is the model trained with feature i ; f_S is another model trained with the retained features; x_S represents the value of the input feature in set S (Chen et al., 2025). Then, through the output of the XGBoost model:

$$g(z') = \phi_0 + \sum_{i=0}^M \phi_i z'_i \quad (2)$$

Where $z' \in \{0,1\}^M$, M is the number of input features, and ϕ_0 is the value of all model outputs (Chen et al., 2025). It is intuitive to use SHAP values to interpret the XGBoost model. $|\phi_i|$ is positively correlated with the impact of the feature on the model.

3. Simulation case study

This paper takes Xiongan New Area in Hebei Province, China as a case study of a water-rich city. First, the WB-RSEI model is used to evaluate the EEQ of the study area, and the Fragstats 4.2 software (McGarigal et al., 2012) is used to extract the 2D/3D landscape morphological index. The raster images are superimposed, and grids of different scales (100m, 200m, 500m, 1000m, 2000m) are set to extract the 2D/3D landscape morphological index and EEQ value within the grid. The XGBoost model plus the SHAP method is used to analyze the regression relationship between the two and find the threshold of the fitting curve. After preliminary research, the results show that:

- (1) The new remote sensing ecological index (WB-RSEI) proposed in this study has better inversion accuracy and robustness; (Figure 2.)
- (2) There is a certain correlation between 3D landscape morphology indicators and ecological environment quality; (Figure 3.)
- (3) There is a threshold for the impact of landscape morphology indicators on urban ecological environment quality;
- (4) The impact of landscape morphology indicators on urban ecological environment quality varies in seasons and scales.

These findings may help to select the most reasonable landscape morphology indicators — optimize urban spatial structure — improve EEQ.

4. Conclusion

Based on regional environmental characteristics, this paper first constructed a water-based remote sensing ecological index (WB-RSEI) suitable for water-rich cities, and took Xiong'an New Area in Hebei Province, China as an example to study the ecological environment quality inversion effect and spatial distribution characteristics of WB-RSEI. The results show that WB-RSEI has a higher credibility than the existing models and can better reflect the ecological environment quality characteristics of Xiong'an New Area. At the same time, this paper conducted a preliminary analysis of the potential influence of 2D/3D landscape morphological indicators including shape complexity (ED, SHDI), connectivity (CONTAG, COHESION, IJI), fragmentation (MPS, LPI) on Eco-Environment Quality. The results show that the landscape morphological pattern has a certain impact on EEQ.

However, the ecological influence of 3D landscape morphological indicators and the regression analysis between landscape morphological pattern factors and ecological environment quality in different seasons, scales and dimensions have not yet been completed. The author will conduct further research in the future.

Figure 2. Comparison of evaluation results between WB-RSEI and RSEI models

Figure 3. Regression relationship between landscape morphology index and EEQ

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Biographies

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Lex Comber is Professor of Spatial Data Analytics, with research interests in all areas of spatial analysis and geocomputation. This year is he is mostly interested in varying coefficient approaches methods and how they interact with spatial and temporal scale.